

Civic participation to fight corruption

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Abstract.

Corruption is an omnipresent problem in all countries, especially connected with public sector and public finance. The goal of this paper is to analyze a selected case of civic participation aimed at fighting the corruption in the Slovak Republic. When fulfilling the goal, we also present preliminary research information collected within the frames of SOLIDUS project - Solidarity in European societies: empowerment, social justice and citizenship. The study uses a qualitative approach to investigate the research question and analyses the original collected survey data from own research as a part of SOLIDUS project. One of important factors greatly influencing the existence of corruption is a high tolerance of citizens for abuse of power and lack of transparency. Research results suggest as a possible solution mobilization and education of citizens in fighting corruption through activities of independent non-governmental organizations.

Keywords: corruption, public finance, civic participation, solidarity

JEL Classification: H39, D73

1 Introduction

The legal definition of corruption for Slovakia is found in the Criminal Code. By law, corruption is defined through its forms, whereby the criminal offense of corruption consists of accepting a bribe, bribery, indirect corruption and electoral corruption. The criterion approach to the definition of corruption is based on a purely legalistic point of view, and thus perceives corruption as conduct that violates applicable laws (a positive approach to the definition of corruption – Staroňová, Sičáková-Beblavá, 2009, p. 12). In the case of violation of laws by persons in public offices, we are discussing deviant action, "which is not in accordance with the standards set for holding public office because of the preference for private benefit (relating to individual persons, families and kindred groups, political or other organizations) in the form of financial (material) position or profit" (Vörös, 2011, p. 2). The prescriptive approach to the definition of corruption declares a breach of ethical standards in order to give priority to one's own interests above the public interest (Staroňová, Sičáková-Beblavá, 2009).

Public interest can be seen as an economic concept (Apgar, Brown, 1987; Bower, 1974; Buchanan, 1996; Hayek, 1994; Nemeč, 1998) and Vörös (2011), Beblavý (2007), Hegemann, Berumen (2011) who see corrupt action as an economic activity that can be described according to the basic rules of the market economy (individuality of actions, conscious of the benefits and costs of such actions in order to maximize one's own advantage).

As already said, there are cases when the society is active and can apply pressure on the responsible behaviour of political institutions. There are several well-known non-governmental organizations that are fighting corruption in various ways, e.g. Transparency International.

Recently, in the focus of many researchers globally solidarity issues have arisen (Lynch et al., 2007; Bjorn, 2010; Fineman, 2010; Cureton, 2012). The recent economic and fiscal crises as well as post-crisis policies of austerity have increased socio-economic inequality and spatial differences between and within the EU member states. The central argument and justification for the solidarity acts is that, while the economic crisis has generat-

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ed new spatial inequalities, there are policies and practices that have been successful in tightening these inequalities and divisions based on solidarity. Solidarity actions are identified at different spatial levels. They can be broken down into actions set out by public institutions and by civic organizations. In this paper we focus on the latter, how civic organizations (e.g. NGOs) help to increase civic participation and thus decrease the level of corruption.

2 Methodology

The goal of this paper is to analyze a selected act of solidarity aimed at fighting the corruption in the Slovak Republic. When fulfilling the goal, we also present preliminary research information collected within the frames of SOLIDUS project - Solidarity in European societies: empowerment, social justice and citizenship.

- The methodology is fully consistent to the methodology of SOLIDUS research project. The selection of case studies followed these criteria:
- There is a clear evidence regarding success (social and/or political impact).
- There is balance between top-down and bottom-up cases selected (i.e. there are cases with citizens, end-users or NGO stakeholders involved, cases with governmental institutions involved and cases with both involvements).
- There is balance among the different policy areas (i.e. housing, employment, health, education and civic engagement).
- At least half of the case studies conducted will be oriented to the fight against poverty and social exclusion.

A main requirement, in relation to the objectives of the SOLIDUS project, is that the cases selected have achieved significant impacts in their particular field of action. With the criteria in mind, we identified 16 cases in Slovakia, out of which 5 were chosen for in-depth analysis using a structured interview. We have followed an interview protocol where all types of involved stakeholders were interviewed (two NGO's representatives and two citizens). In this paper, we present analysis of one of the analyzed cases that focuses on civic engagement fighting the corruption.

The analysis consists of 6 areas that show the outcomes and imply possible policy developments: Democracy, Pluralism, Transparency, Social and political impact, Recognition, Scalability.

3 Analysis

The reason for the creation of and activity of the civic association Against Corruption is the absence of any systematic measures to address the problem of corruption on the part of the state, as evidenced by the low number of corruption cases solved in Slovakia. The current structure of society does not fully respect the rights of the citizen, and the problem of corruption is deepening. In the words of the founder of this NGO, there are several origins of persistent problems of corruption in Slovakia:

A - formal rules:

- There are no clearly defined management and decision-making processes in public administration (in most cases, no standard procedures exist).
- Current legislation and law enforcement leads to the fact that the risk of bearing the consequences of corrupt behavior is less or negligible compared to the profits of such behavior; influenced by the effectiveness of control mechanisms.

B - informal rules:

- The absence of a code of ethics for every employee in public authorities (there are only special provisions for civic service employees).
- A high tolerance of abuse of power and lack of transparency shown by members of the public.

In response to the problem of corruption and the abovementioned reasons the civic association Against Corruption has implemented its activities to involve members of the public in fighting corruption in order to increase the transparency in the management of public funds and the effectiveness of the control mechanisms in public administration.

The association's activities are concentrated on two key areas: 1) educational activities in a wider range (anti-corruption festival, literary competition for secondary school pupils on the theme "Life without Corruption") and 2) address specific corruption cases on the basis of complaints from members of the public.

The civic association in the terms of **democracy** fulfills a democratic way of management, e.g. the educational activities described above are planned and coordinated by mutual discussion of all the members of the association who are also their implementers. Resolving specific corruption cases are not scheduled, but imple-

mented by members of the association on the basis of suggestions from members of the public ("bottom-to-the top").

Pluralism is reflected in implementation of the activities of the association: the key persons for Against Corruption's activities are the four members who coordinate all the activities regarding the fulfilment of the objectives set. They are university educated, socially active people with personal experience in relation to the existence of corruption – a journalist, a local council member, a lawyer and an agent cooperating with the police. When dealing with educational activities on a larger scale (anti-corruption festival, workshops, discussions) volunteers join in. Pluralism can be also seen in the nature of the target group of the association's activities:

- The public in general (increase the sensitivity limit to corruption – by education).
- Members of the public with personal experience of corrupt behavior (detection of corruption cases and their solution).
- Public institutions (control of the management of public resources, pressure on the transparency of how they are used, monitor their progress in addressing specific corruption cases).

In terms of **transparency**, the public is informed about the association's activities and results at the NGO's webpage www.protikorupcii.sk where the association's annual report is made public. Unfortunately, a particular methodology for evaluating the results of operations of the association has not been created. The process of controlling management of funds is set out by the statutes of the association.

Social and political impacts of the association's activities are in two key areas:

1. Education activities of a wider range: anti-corruption festival and literary competition for secondary school pupils on the theme "Life without Corruption". The anti-corruption festival was created with the support of the project Guardian of transparency and democracy in the management of public funds. The project was supported by the NGO Fund which is financed by the EEA Financial Mechanism in 2009 - 2014. The fund manager is the Nadácia otvorenej spoločnosti - Open Society Foundation. The project aims of Guardian of democracy and transparency in the management of public resources is the development of advocacy and watch-dog activities. Against Corruption organized the second annual festival with 500 visitors
2. Address specific corruption cases on the basis of complaints from members of the public. Eleven specific corruption cases based on complaints from citizens were resolved within the activities of the association.

Case #1: The decision of the Planning and Development Office in Žilina in favor of the construction of a self-service carwash on the outskirts of Žilina which was contrary to the town's planning scheme. As a result of the activities of Against Corruption in this case the signing of the final building approval was stopped on an already existing carwash construction. One respondent expressed this about the affair: "I think highly of OZPK (civic association Against Corruption) because it was and still is an organization that acted on and promoted compliance with the law in the contested decisions of Žilina - SÚMŽ (the Planning and Development Office in Žilina). I learned about their project after talking on the phone with the Against Corruption president, Vanda Tuchyňová; the telephone number is clearly and publicly listed on the association's website. Following that at a personal meeting she immediately verified my tip, created the scope for personal meetings and to date OZPK have worked for the benefit of the public, fighting for the respect of laws both verbally and in writing and the personal involvement of employees from the association. In this particular case I participated in decisions about the content which was very current seeing as the association functions very transparently; concerning every step taken in the case I was made aware of and informed about." The respondent then states: "The benefit of resolving our problem is primarily psychological. Every citizen in this country unfortunately knows how small the percentage of the enforcement of their rights still is, especially when they must stand up to the bureaucratic machinery of government. The second benefit is well-founded, without emotion, to begin to solve the problem. In our case, arrange meetings, be it with the Mayor, members of the public or city officials, and promote and describe the situation to the point that the issue (carwash in Strážov) was published on the Internet and in several newspapers and magazines thanks to the addressed journalists. All this thanks only to the civic association. I regard these benefits as being of great importance.

Case #2: A robbery of the Social Insurance Agency in Žilina was paid for by the public, despite the fact that employees of the office flagrantly breached the rules – the money was transported from one place to another in breach of the insurance contract. As a result of the activities of Against Corruption in this case the director of the Social Insurance Agency in Žilina was removed from office.

Case #3: The case: A significant failure in the diversion of public resources in the reconstruction of the square in Liptovský Ján – as a result of the activities of Against Corruption in this case the Director of the Department for Regional Operational Programme Žilina Region was dismissed.

Case #4: A contract about mutual legal assistance between the village of Rosina and a law firm with close ties to the mayor of Rosina was awarded without any tender. Based on this contract the village was bound to pay the law firm 22,500 € over the following 30 months. Due to the intervention of Against Corruption in this case the contract was cancelled by the municipal council of the village.

Case #5: The construction company Váhostav failed to pay more than 100 million € to more than a thousand companies for their work. The company consciously guided itself into restructuring which meant the non-payment of 80% of its receivables in its then condition.

About this affair one respondent expressed the following: "At the time of the outbreak of the Váhostav scandal we were glad to find such an ally as Against Corruption. We were contacted by a specific person from the organization. With the approach of the project organizers I am very happy although at first I found these people to be more good-hearted than active, though of course there are exceptions. In this particular case, we also participated in decisions about the content and progress of the case. In terms of benefits, we found allies for a good and just cause, and within the range of possibilities and of mutual cooperation we participated in practical solutions to issues. Without such assistance it would have been much harder to promote these values, which in this affair was extremely difficult. The prospect of success would have been harder without their participation, and thus also lower. I value the benefits of collaboration with Against Corruption as very significant. The problem, however, was certainly funding which we tried to ensure through our own means from the aggrieved creditors. The project was a success mainly because of the conviction and determination of the people of this project, of course without "our" initiative it would not have worked. The ration expressed was 60/40, i.e. own initiative / project initiatives. The project did not increase my participation in similar activities, but, in the past and at present I am busy with every day cares so that any previous achievement score I value as both forced evil and heroic performance at one and the same time for which an ordinary working man does not have time. I do not know whether the project motivated any increased feelings of solidarity in a particular place or social group, but it certainly earned my respect, although from my point of view this was not just about a "Spartan army"; but together we withstood a much stronger opponent from the "Top" of the private sector. If the project continues, I will certainly recommend it in cases such as ours, which means that matters won't be without any chance of success, but, as in this case, at least get a draw. For me, besides enthusiasts, a project mainly needs sufficient funding so that in order to resolve any case the necessary dynamics won't be slowed down by lack of funds. Such activity should, in my view, be full-time, and should be an alternative as well as an audit institution for common sense and justice; institutionally transparent in our establishment - a corrupt system.

Case #6: The historic landmark Raden house in Čičmany has a reconstructed wooden roof (done in 2010). The wooden shingle used is of very poor quality that does not match the project and has no financial value which the Považské Museum in Žilina paid for. The result of Against Corruption stepping into this case: The Monuments Inspectorate of the Ministry of Culture has ordered the management of Žilina Považské Museum without delay to demand the replacement of the low-quality by the roofing contractor – the company MPM.

Case #7: The director of the regional department of the Slovak Land Fund in the execution of a basic application demanded a 1,000 € bribe. The result of activity by Against Corruption in this case was the sentencing of the director to a 3-year unconditional prison sentence for corruption.

Case #8: Against Corruption implemented an analysis of conducted public procurements in road salt for winter road maintenance in eight regions. It drew attention to the fact that in each autonomous region and for many years a concurrent company (with the occasional exception) has won public procurement and has operated there whereby the number of tenders submitted does not change the fact that it is won again by the same company. It displays the well-tested conditions of participation, linking procurement for three years or more, and thus the chance of success is always to the disadvantage of small businesses that cannot succeed with against the conditions set. It mainly concerns financial turnover for the last three years, where they must demonstrate that they have supplied 30,000 – 60,000 tons of a particular type of road salt; likewise, the amount of security to be proven in advance also spells the death knell for smaller companies.

Case #9: Municipal elections 2014. The publication of campaign funding in elections is a direct means of fighting corruption and cronyism. For this reason, Against Corruption implemented VOLBY OPEN (Open Election) in which we called on candidates for the post of mayors, council leaders and councilors to publish an overview of their election campaign finances. We created a system of data collection so the public could quite easily assess the willingness and level of transparency of individual candidates in the election campaign.

Case #10: A request for the publication of contracts between Žilina Regional Government and selected private companies close to the President of the Slovak Railways (ŽSR); ŽSR (Railways of the Slovak Republic) hired attorneys to negotiate the terms of the publication of said contracts with the chairperson from Against Corruption.

Case #11: In the 2013 autonomous region elections two officials ran for the office of governor in the Žilina Region: Juraj Blanár SMER (the presiding governor) and Miroslav Mikolášik for KDH (MEP). Against Corruption requested both candidates for publication of the details about their campaign financing. One of the candidates, who won the election, refused to disclose the information.

As for the **recognition**, the association has not received any official awards. More areas of the media regularly give positive information about its activities: Markíza, STV, TA3, Žilinský večerník, Nový čas. Association is positively perceived by the public on the association's blog.

In terms of **scalability**, the educational activities of the association in two areas are of a nationwide nature, addressing particular cases is focused on the Žilina region. This issue was described in detail in point on social and political impact.

4 Conclusions

According to the most cited world ranking of perceived corruption from Transparency International, the Slovak Republic ended at the 54th place in 2016. It retained last year's score of 51 out of maximum 100 points. It is also a decrease of four places compared to 2015, while increasing the number of countries rated from 168 to 176 countries. This is the seventh worst place in the EU, when worse than Slovakia were Croatia, Hungary, Romania, Italy, Greece and Bulgaria as the last. The causes of the persistence and even deepening the problem of corruption can be seen at two levels: 1) level of formal rules (legislation, regulation) and 2) the level of informal rules (behavior patterns, customs, traditions).

At the level of formal rules ambiguity and non-transparency of laws or norms creates room for subjective interpretation and decision-making freedom, which increases the risk of corruption. The risk of corruption in this regard is increased by several factors: management and decision-making processes are not clearly defined, criteria and standards are missing or are not clearly defined, current legislation and law enforcement lead to the fact that the risk of bearing the consequences of corrupt behavior is smaller respectively negligible compared to the profits of such behavior. It is influenced by the low efficiency of control mechanisms and low transparency of public funds handling. In this area in the conditions of Slovakia, the executive power is crucial, not a change of laws. Political situation in Slovakia suggests that the fight against corruption will continue in declarative rather than the real level. In 2016 no politician or businessman was convicted of corruption. A disturbing fact is also the indifferent approach of the government to its own anti-corruption measures. For example, the Slovak government has not fulfilled its intention to review the effectiveness of major government spending with system "value for money."

At the level of informal rules, there is a factor of citizens' high tolerance for abuse of power and lack of transparency that significantly influences the existence of corruption. For officials in public procurement there is no code of ethics or other special rules implemented, there are only rules applicable to civil servants. Property of officials in public procurement is not monitored. There are no "black lists" of companies, which in the past were proved to bribe in the procurement process. Positive is the preparation of the amendment on information law, which has the ambition to enhance the right of citizens to information, which would significantly contribute to the activation of citizen participation in the fight against corruption. An example of civic activism in this area is a civic organization "Against corruption", whose activities were analyzed as an example of good practice to fight corruption at the level of informal rules through mobilization and education of citizens.

Acknowledgements

The research SOLIDUS leading to these results received funding from the H2020 Programme of the European Commission under Grant Agreement n° 649489.

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